

THE INFLUENCE OF THE EAST ON RUSSIAN LITERATURE

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Annotation: The article explores the long and rich path of interaction between the East and Russian literature. Beginning with early contacts and extending to modern literary movements, the author examines how Eastern themes and motifs have become integrated into the artistic heritage, influencing the style, plot and aesthetics of Russian literature.

Keywords: East, Russian literature, cultural connections, influence, romanticism, literary aesthetics, dialogue of cultures.

Cultural interactions play a key role in the evolution of literature, enriching the creative palette and expanding the boundaries of artistic perception. One of the most important elements of this dialogue was the influence of Eastern literature on the development of Russian literature. In this introduction we will outline the significance of these cultural interactions and briefly examine the key points in which Eastern influence has left an indescribable imprint on the Russian literary tradition. When different literary traditions come together, a unique cultural dialogue occurs, resulting in new ideas, perspectives, and styles. In the context of Russian literature, interaction with Eastern culture represents a special cultural aspect that has made a significant contribution to the formation of the literary canon.

The history of the influence of Eastern literature on Russian literature has many key moments stretching across centuries. Since early contacts with eastern cultures, oriental motifs have penetrated into ancient Russian literature, giving it unique features. This cultural exchange took on new dimensions in the era of Peter I, when the discovery of the West was also accompanied by Eastern inspirations.

The emergence of the Russian literary tradition is closely related to early contacts with Eastern cultures. In ancient times, trade and cultural ties with the East, including Persian, Arab and Chinese civilizations, introduced new ideas and artistic elements into Russian literature. Such contacts became the starting point for cultural exchange, thanks to which the unique features of Russian literature were formed.

Early translations of Eastern texts, as well as the exchange of literary forms and genres, promoted mutual understanding between cultures. Eastern

examples of literature penetrated Russian works, opening new horizons and stimulating artistic creativity.

In ancient Russian literature, oriental motifs had a profound influence on the formation of literary style.

It all started with the journey of a medieval merchant from Tver, Afanasy Nikitin, who, being a reluctant traveler, left his mark on history thanks to his wonderful essay "Walking across Three Seas". This work widely and variedly describes the lands of Iran, Turkey, Arab principalities and India, presenting readers of old Rus' of the 15th century with many amazing impressions. Nikitin, as a trade researcher, learned and saw a lot. His work is the first description of a commercial trip in Russian literature, rich in observations about the political system, economy and culture of other countries. He was the first to describe Islam from the inside. When it came to religion, Nikitin switched to the Arabic-Turkic-Persian colloquial language, and when he wrote about worldly affairs and the deeds of influential personalities, he kept notes in Russian. In his travel notes, Nikitin says: "I met many Indians and told them about my faith, that I was not a Muslim, but a Christian. They did not hide their food, their trade, their prayers, or their women. they did not hide from me. I asked them many questions about their faith, and they answered: we believe in Adam, and God is Adam and his race. There are 84 faiths in India, and all believers believe in God. Faith does not drink, He doesn't eat, he doesn't marry." In his notes, Nikitin also paid special attention to India: "In India there is a special country where everyone walks naked, their heads are not covered, their breasts are open, their hair is braided in one braid, everyone exists with enlarged bellies and they have many children who are born every year "Men and women all walk naked, all black. Wherever I go, people look at me in surprise because I am a white man..." [1]. The records of Afanasy Nikitin were discovered by N.I. Karamzin in the archives of the Trinity-Sergius Monastery and published in 1817 as part of the Trinity Chronicle.

The 19th century brought a new stage in Russian literature in interaction with Eastern culture. Writers and poets sought to explore oriental themes, seeing in them a source of exoticism, mystery and philosophical depth. Alexander Sergeevich Griboyedov, an outstanding Russian poet and playwright, the representative of Russia in Persia, was familiar with Islam and was passionate about it, which was reflected in his classic and profound Russian play "Woe from Wit." Alexander Sergeevich Pushkin also showed an unusual and respectful attitude towards the Koran and Islam in his mysterious, mysterious

and magnificent works, including “Imitation of the Koran”. Much research has been devoted to this cycle of works, and many people have wondered how a young poet, raised in far northern Russia under the auspices of the Imperial Lyceum, was able to penetrate so deeply into the spirit, style and beauty of the Koran? Pushkin was aware of their greatness and noted that “many moral truths are presented in the Koran with force and poetry.” The nine poems included in this cycle are true masterpieces of poetry. Pushkin revealed the mysterious East for the Russian reader in works such as “Prisoner of the Caucasus” and “Bakhchisarai Fountain”, the poem “Gaziy”, the poems “Our Giaurs Glorify Istanbul”, “Delibash” and others. Muslim heroes, askers, warriors and righteous people fill the poems of Pushkin's contemporaries. They, while maintaining their Christian faith, were inspired by the courage, perseverance and incredible devotion to the faith of the representatives of Islam. (Alexander Vyazemsky - “Mukhamed”, Alexey Shishkov - “Osman”, Andrey Muravyov - “Song of the Dervishes” and “Bakhchisarai”, Vladimir Benediktov - “Caliph and Slave”, “Abdel Koder’s Letter”. A completely unexpected Muslim theme can also be seen in the poems Fyodor Ivanovich Tyutchev: “Oleg's Shield.”

Eastern literary schools, such as Persian and Arabic, became sources of inspiration for writers, enriching the Russian literary tradition with variety and depth. The reflection of Eastern ideas in the works of the 19th century created a unique synthesis that united Western and Eastern literary traditions.

In modern Russian literature, oriental themes continue to have a noticeable influence, giving the works depth and a special atmosphere. Modern writers and poets actively exploit oriental motifs, creating unique artistic images and revealing new facets of human experience.

The works of such authors as Tatyana Tolstaya and Vladimir Sorokin demonstrate the influence of oriental themes in modern prose. Eastern motifs become a means of self-expression, helping authors explore the complex internal states of characters and embody new ideas.

Analyzing the centuries-old path of interaction between the East and Russian literature, we see how oriental themes and motifs were firmly woven into the artistic heritage. From early contacts in antiquity to the era of romanticism and modernity, the influence of the East has manifested itself in various forms: from folklore to romantic poetry, from classical works to modern literary movements.

Oriental images have become an integral part of the literary language, penetrating the works of great Russian writers and leaving their mark in the

formation of literary aesthetics. This mosaic path of harmony and mutual influence has become an important component of cultural heritage.

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